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System Integration of an Instrumented Tidal Research Turbine Testbed for Open-Source R&D

Parviz Sedigh^{a1}, Martin Wosnik^a, Mason Bichanich^a, Kenneth Lannamann^a, Vincent Neary^b, Aidan Bharath^c, Robert Cavagnaro^d

^aAtlantic Marine Energy Center (AMEC), University of New Hampshire (UNH), USA

^bSandia National Laboratories (SNL), USA

^cNational Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL), USA

^dPacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL), USA

Abstract

Tidal turbines harness the kinetic energy of tidal currents for clean and renewable power. This project aims to build and deploy an instrumented marine turbine system in a real tidal environment to serve as an open-source test bed for open-source research and development. The chosen turbine type is a three-bladed axial-flow turbine.

The project is a collaboration between Sandia National Laboratories (SNL), the University of New Hampshire (UNH)/Atlantic Marine Energy Center (AMEC), the National Renewable Energy Laboratory (NREL) and the Pacific Northwest National Laboratory (PNNL).

The turbine system includes a nacelle, a 2.5 m diameter rotor with hub and blades, motor/generator, gearbox, tower with a yaw drive, a large number of sensors, and data cables. The turbine system integration, which will take place at UNH/AMEC in collaboration with partners SNL, NREL, and PNNL is a critical task prior to system testing and deployment. Blades will be machined, equipped with sensors, and calibrated before assembly. Motor control and instrumentation will be integrated into a UNH-built variant of the NREL-MODAQ. Dry and leak tests will be conducted before deploying the turbine at the UNH Pier facilities. The goal is to optimize performance, efficiency, and reliability, requiring expertise in various disciplines. This contribution will provide an update on the Instrumented Tidal Turbine Testbed's system integration.

Keywords: axial flow turbine; system integration; marine turbine; renewable energy; energy converter

1. Introduction

Tidal currents, also known as tidal streams, are the horizontal movements of water caused by the gravitational interactions between the Earth, the Moon, and the Sun. They provide a vast source of energy that can cover a large energy demand. The potential tidal resource in the US varies along its coastlines. The Atlantic coast has higher tidal ranges and stronger currents compared to the Pacific coast, making it more suitable for tidal energy generation. Tidal

* Corresponding author.

E-mail address: parviz.sedigh@unh.edu

turbines are a type of current energy converters (CEC) that enables us to harness the kinetic energy of tidal currents to generate clean and renewable power. Tidal turbines are made of several principal components and subsystems [1]. *Turbine system integration* refers to the process of effectively combining and coordinating various components and subsystems of a tidal turbine to create a functional and efficient overall system. The goal of system integration is to optimize the performance, reliability, and overall energy output of the tidal turbine while ensuring safe and stable operation.

This project is aimed to design, build, and deploy an instrumented marine turbine system in a real tidal environment to serve as a marine turbine test bed for conducting open-source research and development (R&D) and for generating and disseminating open-source datasets on power performance, mechanical and design loads, and tidal inflow conditions which will provide feedback on marine IEC standards as well as enabling comprehensive model verification and validation [2] for digital twinning and numerical models. In this paper we aimed to present the *System Integration* process that makes our system ready for deployment through describing main components of this axial flow tidal turbine system, its integration, testing and operation process as well as the preparation before turbine deployment in an actual tidal flow environment.

Nomenclature

UNH	University of New Hampshire
AMEC	Atlantic Marine Energy Center
SNL	Sandia National Laboratories
NREL	National Renewable Energy Laboratory
PNNL	Pacific Northwest National Laboratory
CEC	Current Energy Converter
MODAQ	Modular Ocean Data Acquisition
DAQ	Data Acquisition
TDP	Turbine Deployment Platform
TEC	Tidal Energy Converter
FEA	Finite Element Analysis
GBE	Great Bay Estuary
ADCP	Acoustic Doppler Current Profiler
VPN	Virtual Private Network

2. Turbine System Integration

The turbine system integration will be performed at the AMEC, UNH, in collaboration with partners SNL, NREL and PNNL.

The turbine system is divided into a nacelle, rotor with hub and three blades [3], and tower with a yaw drive. The order of assembly was carefully considered during the design process. A liftable rack will be designed to house the power electronics and motor/generator controls. Motor control and instrumentation will be integrated into a UNH-built variant of the NREL Modular Ocean Data Acquisition (MODAQ) system [4]. Once the assembly process and system integration are completed in the UNH Olson Center, the turbine will be mounted on a test stand for a dry test, during which it will be rotated via motor to check system mechanical integrity, instrumentation and if all the components are working together. After successful dry testing, a leak test will be conducted, with compressed gas and/or in the engineering tank in Ocean Engineering Laboratory. After the successful completion of these tests and confirming the turbine system's mechanical integrity and overall operability, the turbine will be transferred to the UNH Pier Facilities to be prepared for deployment at real environment.

2.1. Sensors & Measurements

Once of the main objectives of this project is to provide a comprehensive dataset for power performance, mechanical and design loads, and tidal inflow conditions of an axial flow tidal turbine working in a real tidal flow environment. To do so, we need to implement several sensors and devices in our turbine system that will able us to

measure the required parameters. Fig. 1. categorizes the set of parameters that we aimed to measure and the list of the sensors/instruments that will able us to do that.

Fig. 1. measurement purposes & list of sensors

From Fig. 1, one can imagine the extensive set off data that will be available once the axial flow tidal turbine is deployed in a real tidal flow environment. This achievement will help marine energy industries make more progress.

2.2. Nacelle & Rotor

The nacelle includes the motor/generator, a gearbox, shaft and bearings, a slipring to transfer power and data to/from the hub, seals, various sensors, as well as penetrations for power and data cables. The 2.5 m diameter rotor includes the hub, three instrumented blades each with 1043.3 mm length, an optical interrogator for fiberoptic strain gages, a data acquisition system for sensors and blades, blade-hub attachments, and seals. Fig. 2. shows a cross-section view of the designed nacelle and rotor, including hub and blades as well as the arrangement of the nacelle components.

Fig. 2. a) components of nacelle and hub b) turbine system connected to tower

2.3. Blade Scan

Ensuring the quality and accuracy of turbine blades is essential to ensure the safe and efficient operation of turbines throughout their service life. Blade quality checks are performed during the system integration process. This process will be done by scanning the manufactured blades via a 3D scanner that is available at the UNH Olson Advanced Manufacturing Center, to ensure that the blades are produced to the correct specifications and dimensions, and is necessary to detect any damage, crack, wear, or deformations on the blade's surface which might happen during the production process. After the blade has been checked and dimensions confirmed, a thin protective coating (Cerakote) will be applied and they will be shipped to SNL to be equipped with optical strain gauges and calibrated. Afterwards, the blades will be shipped back to UNH Olson Center where they will be integrated into the turbine system.

2.4. Test Stand & Yaw Drive

A test stand provides a platform to evaluate the functionality, efficiency, and durability of tidal turbine before its deployment. One of the major portions of the system integration process is the component testing where each individual component of the tidal turbine will need to be tested independently to ensure they meet design specifications and function reliably.

A proposed design for the test stand is illustrated in fig. 3. Simplicity and manufacturability are of high interest for the design of the test stand in this project. To this end, the proposed model consists of an off-the-shelf steel plate, and steel pipe welded to it, supported by a number of steel gussets. The test stand will be anchored to the ground to provide more rigidity during the component integration process. The designed test stand will also serve as assembly stand by using a adaptive brachet that will let the us have access to the wires, cables, glands and tubes that will be aout from the mid-nacelle penetration port & access window. After conducting Finite Element Analysis (FEA) on several design iterations for the bolt and gusset patterns, the proposed one showed reasonable and more reliable results of strength yield of the material for the input forces. Fig. 4. shows the FEA results, using SolidWorks, for the proposed test stand design. In this analysis, the foundation bolts were considered as fixture of the bolt pattern, a normal force of 14.7 kN (1500 kg), and a thrust force of 3 kN, which are both conservative estimates. The center of gravity of the turbine system (nacelle + rotor) has a slight offset from the pipe centerline with a value of 168.45 mm in X, -476.36 mm in Y, and 0.42 mm in Z direction, and bolting the test stand to the ground will add safety against tipping over.

Fig. 3. test stand designed

Fig. 4. FEA analysis of the designed test stand

One of the goals of this project is to deploy and recover the turbine under a variety of flow conditions and allowing for yaw adjustment of the turbine during testing safely and effectively. To do that, a yaw mechanism for the turbine was designed. Fig. 5. shows the proposed yaw mechanism, with yaw drives mounted above the water line.

Fig. 5. yaw drive mechanism

The tower is constructed using a 14" diameter schedule 80 steel pipe, firmly fixed within a mounting bracket that connects to the pitching mechanism, as shown in Fig. 3. The yaw adjustment can be made continuously and locked down in 5-degree increments ranging from -30 to +30 degrees in relation to the principal long axis of the platform using a motor. The yaw drive design will be considered final once turbine system design details are confirmed, and it is scheduled for completion in Q2, March 2024.

2.5. Data Acquisition

Data acquisition (DAQ) systems play a crucial role in recording important parameters and performance metrics during testing and operation for the purpose of analysis, monitoring, control, or other applications. The Modular Ocean Data Acquisition (MODAQ) system will be the primary DAQ for measurement requirements for turbine loads and power performance metrics. MODAQ was developed by NREL [4], and for the purpose of this project a UNH-built variant of it will be utilized. MODAQ will also be utilized as a turbine health monitoring platform and be actively linked with the PTO for both data gathering tasks and simple control. MODAQ will be actively accessible via VPN from anywhere off the test platform and will make use of the MODAQ cloud capabilities to actively move data off the platform for automated analysis during data acquisition periods. Fig. 6. shows the MODAQ that was built by UNH and will be incorporated in this project as a turbine control and data acquisition system.

Fig. 6. modular data acquisition system built by UNH

2.6. Dry & Leak testing

Dry test refers to tests that assess the mechanical behavior of the turbine components, such as the structural integrity of the blades, gearbox, and generator, as well as its instrumentation without involving the actual tidal flow around the turbine. Before assembling turbine components, each part as well as sensors will go through a functionality test and inspection to make sure they have the operability condition. Once the assembly process and system integration are completed, the turbine will be mounted on a test stand for a dry test at the UNH Olson Center, during which it will be rotated via motor through its full operational envelope to check for its integrity and see if all the components are working together. Afterwards, A pressurization/vacuum leak test of the nacelle and hub assembly will be performed in the laboratory by creating the same pressure difference as during the in-water deployment, but with air on both the outside and inside. This will ensure use that our turbine systems' components are perfectly sealed against any water penetration. A vacuum will be created inside the nacelle and hub to a gage pressure comparable to the approximate hydrostatic pressure the turbine nacelle and hub will experience while deployed, approximately 0.2 bar. This is considered a more rigorous leak test than testing under water, due to the small size of air or inert gas (N₂) molecules. Pressure will be monitored with pressure gages or sensors. Once the confidence of turbine integrity achieved, the entire turbine system will be transported to UNH research pier for a before deployment set up & installations.

3. Pre- deployment & Final Steps

The Great Bay estuarine (GBE) system is one of the most energetic tidally driven systems on the East Coast of the United States. Tidal current speeds over 2.8 m/s have been observed with 2-minute ensemble averaged ADCP measurements and instantaneous, local current speeds over 3.3 m/s with 16 Hz ADV measurements [5]. The UNH-AMEC tidal energy test site is located at the Memorial Bridge crossing the Piscataqua River in Portsmouth, NH on the GBE system. Fig. 7. (a) shows a render of the designed turbine attached to UNH Turbine Deployment Platform and fig. 7. (b) shows the UNH Turbine Deployment Platform (TDP) connected to the bridge pier at the test site.

Before turbine deployment, the TDP will be transferred to UNH Pire Facility (Judd Gregg Marine Research Center) located at Newcastle, NH to make the platforms ready to install the turbine to the turbine. Check of instrumentation and some in- situ processes like alignments & adjustments & check will happen here. The turbine system will slowly be operated to safely check integrity of dynamic seals. Once the turbine is secured on the deployment platform, they will be transferred to the test site for the actual deployment.

Fig. 7. UNH-AMEC TDP (a) render of SolidWorks (b) connected to the bridge pier at Piscataqua River in Portsmouth, NH

Moreover, several tasks will need to be performed in parallel during the system integration process. The MODAQ data acquisition system will be modified to add new sensors and the electrical infrastructure will need to be upgraded. TDP will be moved to the UNH Pier for modifications, like structural change to eliminate pier shear flow turbulence effect on the platform moon pool and adjusting the turbine pitching mechanism to be ready to be connected to the axial flow turbine.

4. Summary

System integration for an axial flow tidal turbine refers to the process of putting things together to make the turbine work. This process includes the mechanical, instruments & electronical integration of the components that were designed, prepared, and tested in advance. Once functionality is confirmed, they are going to be housed in the nacelle and rotor. This process will happen on a test stand designed and purpose-built for this project which will allow us to rotate the turbine with a motor. The entire assembly will go through a leak test to make sure the connections are waterproof. The UNH-built MODAQ system will be used for all the measurements during the test and deployment. The deployment will happen at UNH-AMEC tidal energy test site, located at the Memorial Bridge crossing the Piscataqua River in Portsmouth, NH, an energetic tidally driven estuarine system.

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